

Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature ($27 \pm 1^\circ$). Electronic spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK-2 spectrophotometer.

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Study of some Transition Metal Complexes of Cephaloridine

PURUSHOTTAM B. CHAKRAWARTI*, BHARATI SRIVASTAVA and B. L. VIJAYVARGIYA

Chemistry Department, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidhyalaya, Bhopal

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Cephaloridine is bactericidal and acts similarly as penicillins. Although much work has been done on the metal complexes of penicillin G and V, practically no work is available on the metal complexes of cephaloridine. Hence the present communication reports the results of our studies on complexation reaction of cephaloridine with some biologically important metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric¹ and potentiometric (pH) studies indicate that cephaloridine forms 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with the metal ions.

A perusal of the pH-titration curves indicates liberation of only one proton during complexation of each molecule of the drug,

The study of the formation curves indicates that complexation of cephaloridine takes place in step-wise manner (except Cu^{II}, which involves simultaneous formation of the complexes). The low-values of stability constants (Table 1) show that the interaction of the drug with the metal ions is ionic.

The analytical data (Table 2) indicate that the composition of the complexes is ML₂H₂O. Ir spectra of the complexes indicate that the linking of the drug molecule with the metal ions is through the nitrogen of the β-lactam thiazolidine ring and carboxylate ion forming a five-membered ring. Ir spectra show that, while most of the bands of the ligands remain unchanged on complexation, there

is a considerable shift in the frequencies of tertiary nitrogen of carboxylic group of the ring. The β-lactam amide band in the drugs appearing at

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME CEPHALORIDINE COMPLEXES

μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄), Temp. = 30°

Metal(II) complex	log K		log K ₂		log k ₂		ΔG ₁	ΔG ₂	ΔG _n
	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)			
Mg	3.37	3.77	2.05	2.07	5.80	5.84	2.28	1.25	3.53
Mn	4.48	3.55	2.72	2.92	7.20	7.47	2.75	1.77	4.52
Fe	4.72	4.84	3.38	3.32	7.10	7.80	2.93	2.01	4.94
Ni	4.45	4.70	2.70	2.60	7.15	7.39	2.85	1.63	4.48
Co	4.22	4.24	3.69	3.71	7.90	7.95	2.57	2.25	4.82
Zn	4.48	4.46	3.62	3.64	8.10	8.10	2.70	2.20	4.90
K _H	6.91*								

(a)=Graphical method, (b)=least-square method, (*)=pointwise calculation.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					
		Metal	C	H	N	S	H ₂ O
MgL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Yellow)	126	5.11 (5.13)	48.02 (48.14)	4.42 (4.43)	8.84 (8.86)	13.47 (13.51)	7.53 (7.60)
MnL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Pale yellow)	215	10.86 (10.88)	45.11 (45.22)	4.15 (4.16)	8.31 (8.33)	12.66 (12.69)	7.12 (7.11)
FeL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Dark brown)	>320	11.02 (11.04)	45.03 (45.14)	4.14 (4.15)	8.29 (8.32)	12.64 (12.67)	7.11 (7.12)
NiL ₂ H ₂ O ^b (Green)	186	11.52 (11.55)	44.77 (44.88)	4.12 (4.13)	8.24 (8.26)	12.56 (12.59)	7.06 (7.08)
CuL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Dark green)	125	12.35 (12.38)	44.35 (44.46)	4.08 (4.09)	8.17 (8.19)	12.45 (12.48)	7.00 (7.02)
ZnL ₂ H ₂ O ^a (Pale yellow)	188	12.65 (12.69)	44.20 (44.31)	4.07 (4.08)	8.14 (8.16)	12.40 (12.43)	6.97 (6.99)

^aSparingly soluble in acetone and ethanol. ^bSparingly soluble in acetic acid and acetone.